

Obtaining the Quantum $\exp(ipx)$ From Pauli Matrices?

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We have pointed out in previous notes that the free particle wavefunction $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ holds for both a photon and particle with rest mass, while the latter has spin $\frac{1}{2}$ and the former, spin 1. We thus suggested that spin is obtained in a very different manner from $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. Here, we start with the Lorentz invariant $-EE + p \cdot p c^2 = -m_0^2 c^4$ ((1)) and argue, as in (1), that it must be linearized to obtain a linear equation in the intrinsic force, namely m_0 which is linked to inertia, because force acts in a linear form in nature (e.g. $F=dp/dt$). At this point, however, p is a vector and there is no concept of $\hbar \text{grad}$. One may mathematically linearize ((1)) using the approach of Dirac (except that now p is a vector of numbers not an operator). This leads to 4×4 matrices with off diagonal Pauli matrices (multiplied by 1 and -1). One may see that the rotational invariant $p \cdot p$ may be linearized to $s \cdot p$ ($s =$ three 2×2 Pauli matrices) because these matrices anticommute. Thus, a 2×2 Pauli matrix is associated with rotational invariance. At this point, this Pauli matrix is simply a math entity. In terms of measurement, given that one has matrices, there are also commutation relations which are important.

One may consider another math operator linked with rotational invariance, namely $d/d\phi$ for a rotation about a z-axis. In classical physics, one does not have such a derivative appearing as one deals with functions. If $d/d\phi$ is an operator generating rotations, then d/dx should generate translations, but this is simply math. The "catch" seems to be that if one introduces a probability $f(x,p)$ (which is unusual because $P(x)dx = dx/L$, where L is an arbitrary length), then $f(p_1,x)f(p_2,x)=f(p_3,x)f(p_4,x)$ if $p_1+p_2=p_3+p_4$ (we use 1-dimension for simplicity). One may, however, shift this equation to $x+dx$ which implies that $df(p_1)/dx f(p_2) + f(p_1)df(p_2)/dx = df(p_3)/dx f(p_4) + f(p_3) df(p_4)/dx$. A solution which keeps p present is: $\exp(i C p x)$. We use i because we want to have equal modulus at all x points. If $C=1$, the one has $\exp(i p x)$ with $-id/dx$ as the operator which retrieves p . One may then apply this idea to $L = r \times p$ and find that this new operator commutes like the Pauli matrices and gives rise to $d/d\phi$, the rotational operator postulated above. Thus, it seems that one could start with the notion of spin and obtain the notion of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, we argue and spin being linked to angular momentum, we argue.

Spin for a Particle with Rest Mass and the Notion of an Operator Linked with Rotational Invariance

We argued in (1), that one may obtain the notion of spin by finding an equation that is linear in the intrinsic force of a particle with rest mass and is also linked to p , E and geometry. In such a case, we suggest that m_0 , the rest mass, represents inertia and that this is the intrinsic force. This force should appear linearly in an equation (just like $F=dp/dt$). To find such an equation, one may linearize the Lorentz invariant:

$$-EE + c^2 p \cdot p = -m_0^2 c^4 \quad ((1))$$

This linearization has been done by Dirac and leads to 4x4 matrices which contain the Pauli 2x2 matrices as off-diagonal submatrices (multiplied by 1 and -1). If one examines the structure of Pauli matrices, one sees that:

$$S_i * S_j - S_j * S_i = \epsilon_{ijk} S_k \quad ((2)) \quad \text{Here } \epsilon_{ijk} \text{ is the Levi-Civita symbol. } (2)$$

Thus, an operator is linked with rotational invariance, but this operator is a set of three 2x2 matrices. One may ask whether there is any link with classical dynamics.

Translational and Rotational Operators In Classical Physics

Newtonian mechanics and special relativity do not require that one introduce an operator associated with rotational invariance. If one had to create an operator demonstrating rotational invariance in a math sense, one might propose:

$$d/d\phi, \text{ for rotation about the z-axis } ((3))$$

In such a case, d/dx is a translation operator. This is well-known math, so what does it have to do with physical reality?

We suggest that one might postulate a physical probability function to describe conservation of momentum through:

$$f(p_1, x) f(p_2, x) = f(p_3, x) f(p_4, x) \text{ if } p_1 + p_2 = p_3 + p_4 \text{ (we use 1-dimension for simplicity)} \quad ((4))$$

Here x ensures that the conservation of momentum in a 2-body collision occurs at the point x. One could, however, shift this point to x+dx yielding:

$$df_1/dx f_2 + f_1 df_2/dx = df_3/dx f_4 + f_3 df_4/dx \quad ((5))$$

Two possible solutions are $f = \exp(C x)$ and $f = \exp(C p x)$ due to the understood conservation of momentum. We choose the later because it includes p in $f(p, x)$ and use:

$$\exp(ipx) \quad ((5))$$

This may be generalized to $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ ((6))

Thus, there seems to be a physical entity ((6)), a strange kind of probability for conservation of momentum which is linked to $P(x)dx = dx/L$, where L is an arbitrary length, through

$$\exp(-ipx)/\sqrt{L} \exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L} = 1/L \quad ((7))$$

The question then becomes: What about $d/d\phi$? One could introduce $\exp(i(L_z)\phi)$ where L_z is angular momentum about the z-axis and make the same arguments as above, but there is already a classical definition for angular momentum, namely:

$$L = r \times p \quad (8)$$

We consider the operators L_x, L_y (with $-i\hbar/dx$ for p_x and $-i\hbar/dy$ for p_y) and check if there is any association with the Pauli matrix result, i.e. with L_z . We also check if L_z is linked with $d/d\phi$. If so, then it would seem that the Pauli matrices are associated with some kind of angular motion.

We test : $L_i L_j - L_j L_i = \epsilon_{ilm} x_l \hbar \partial_m \epsilon_{jrs} x_r \hbar \partial_s + \epsilon_{jrs} x_r \hbar \partial_s \epsilon_{ilm} x_l \hbar \partial_m$ where $\partial_m = d/dx_m$.

$$= \epsilon_{ilm} \epsilon_{jrs} x_l \{ \partial(m,r) \hbar \partial_s + x_r \hbar \partial_m \partial_x \} + \epsilon_{jrs} \epsilon_{ilm} x_i \{ \partial(ls) \hbar \partial_m + x_k \hbar \partial_s \partial_m \}$$

One may note that the terms with double derivatives cancel because they are the same for $L_i L_j$ and $L_j L_i$.

$$\text{The other terms are: } \epsilon_{ilm} \epsilon_{jrs} x_l \hbar \partial(mr) \partial_s - \epsilon_{jrs} \epsilon_{ilm} x_r \hbar \partial(ls) \partial_m = \\ -\{d(ij) \hbar \partial(ls) - d(is) \hbar \partial(lj)\} x_l \partial_x - \{d(ji) \hbar \partial(rm) - d(jm) \hbar \partial(ri)\} x_i \partial_m$$

$$= x_j \hbar \partial_i - x_i \hbar \partial_j \rightarrow L_z \quad (\text{here } d(ij) \text{ is the Kronecker delta and } d(ij)=0 \text{ because } i \neq j. \quad (8))$$

$$\text{For a Pauli matrix, one should also have: } [s_i, s_j] = i2 \epsilon_{ijk} s_k \quad (9)$$

The L_i operators and the Pauli matrices are both linked with rotational motion-invariance and share the same commutation relation.

The Pauli matrices satisfy: $s_i s_j + s_j s_i = 2 \delta_{ij} I(2 \times 2)$ where $I(2 \times 2)$ is the 2×2 identity matrix. This is used to create $p \cdot p$. Such a relation does not hold for L_i and L_j . Nevertheless, it is the commutation relation which is of interest for measurements and in such a case, L_i and s_i behave in the same way suggesting that they both seem to be related to rotation.

Interestingly, it is the anticommutation behaviour of the Pauli s_i 's which is linked to linearizing $p \cdot p$ (which is rotationally invariant), giving rise to the s_i 's, but then measurement considerations show that s_i, s_j commute in the same manner as L_i, L_j .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ and spin arise in completely different ways. In (1), we argued that spin for a particle with rest mass arises by trying to find an equation linear in the intrinsic force (mass or inertia) as forces appear linearly in nature ($F = dp/dt$). This means linearizing $-E^2 + c^2 p \cdot p = -m^2 c^4$ as Dirac did, giving rise to 4×4 matrices which contain the Pauli matrices. The anticommutation relations of Pauli matrices are key in this calculation, but given that one obtains operators (matrices), one may also consider the commutation

relations which are linked to measurements in opposite order. One may then ask: Are there any other operators which may be linked to rotational invariance? An obvious math possibility is $d/d\phi$ (for symmetry about the z -axis). This suggests d/dx for translation (i.e. the translational generator). We argue that the latter may find physical meaning if one introduces an unusual probability $f(p,x)$ which ensures momentum conservation, i.e. $f(p_1,x)f(p_2,x)=f(p_3,x)f(p_4,x)$ if $p_1+p_2=p_3 + p_4$ (1-dimension for simplicity). We then show that the operator d/dx arises naturally and calculate the commutation $L_iL_j - L_jL_i$ using $-id/dx$ in place of p_x etc. This leads to the same commutation result as the Pauli matrices suggesting that they are both related to some kind of rotational motion. We note that the commutator is of interest as it is linked to measurements in different orders. As a result, we suggest that by starting with the notion of spin $\frac{1}{2}$ and operators, one is led to the operator d/dx and the operator $L=r \times p$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on Quantum Spin, Intrinsic Force and Special Relativity (preprint, zenodo, 2026)
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pauli_matrices